

ЕПТЕЛІАЛЬНО-МЕЗЕНХІМАЛЬНИЙ ПЕРЕХІД В ПРОТОКОВІЙ АДЕНОКАРЦИНОМІ ПІДШЛУНКОВОЇ ЗАЛОЗИ В ЗАЛОЖНОСТІ ВІД РОЗМІРУ ПУХЛИНИ

EPITHELIAL-MESENCHYMAL TRANSITION IN DUCTAL ADENOCARCINOMA OF THE PANCREAS DEPENDING ON THE SIZE OF THE TUMOR

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The aim of the study is to analyze histological and immune-histochemical (IHC) examinations of epithelial-mesenchymal transition (EMT) in pancreatic ductal adenocarcinoma (PDAC) with tumors <3 cm and >3 cm.

Materials and methods: the results of pathomorphological and IHC examinations of 49 cases of surgical material taken from patients with PDAC have been complexly assessed. Group I (26 cases) includes tumors <3 cm in size, group II (23 cases) comprises tumors >3 cm in size. Paraffin serial sections were prepared by hematoxylin and eosin staining, Masson-trichrome method. IHC examination was performed using primary antibodies against E-cadherin and β -catenin, smooth muscle actin (α -SMA), and vimentin (Vim). The relative area of expression of immunopositive cells in the IHC examination was determined by digital photometry in 5 fields of view of the microscope ($\times 200$) and processed with the medical software "ImageJ". The data were statistically processed with the licensed software "STATISTICA 13.0".

Results: Microscopic examination revealed heterogeneity of PDAC histoarchitecture. The glandular-ductal compartment prevails on the periphery of the tumor. In the center of the tumor, there is a dense mesenchymal component, represented by spindle-shaped cells and an extracellular matrix. In group I, the glandular-ductal compartment consisted of small cancerous, glandular tubules and trabeculae, in group II – from large similar structures and large clusters of small cancer cells. In group II, the stromal component occupied a larger area of the tumor than in group I ($p < 0.05$). The expression of diffuse brown E-cadherin with membrane-cytoplasmic localization with a significantly more pronounced decrease in the marker in the second group than in the first group was detected in the duct structures. ($p < 0.05$).

In the EMT zone, a similar expression of E-cadherin was detected in clusters of cancer-altered cells without a significant difference between groups ($p > 0.05$). Expression of β -catenin in the ductal system of PADC and in the EMT zone was observed as diffuse brown membrane-cytoplasmic staining. In group I, loss of β -catenin was observed in the duct system in comparison with the EMT zone. In group II, the expression of β -catenin did not differ significantly between the duct compartment and the EMT zone. The expression of mesenchymal markers also had significant diffuse brown membrane-cytoplasmic staining of spindle-shaped cells around small cancerous tubules and large trabeculae. Expression of α -SMA in group I was 1.5 times less than in group II ($p < 0.05$). Expression of Vim in group II was insignificantly lower than in group I. ($p > 0.05$). Correlation analysis (Pearson's coefficient) between epithelial and mesenchymal markers revealed weak feedback ($p > 0.05$) in group I, as well as moderate feedforward connection ($p < 0.05$) in group II.

Conclusions: With the progression of PADC development, there is a progression of EMT, accompanied by an increased aberrant expression of relevant markers.